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KINETICS AND MECHANISM OF OXIDATION OF AZO DYE ACID YELLOW 36 BY CHLORAMINE-T IN HYDROCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

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ABSTRACT

Kinetics of oxidative decolorization of Acid yellow36 (AY36) by chloramine-T, (CAT) in hydrochloric acid (HCl) medium at 301 K has been investigated spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 439nm. The reaction showed first order dependence on [CAT] and [AY36]₀ and inverse fractional order dependence on [HCl]. Stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 1:3 with respect to the substrate and oxidant respectively. The oxidation products were identified by spectral analysis. Variation of ionic strength had no effect on the rate. Addition of p-toluene sulfanamide (PTS) retarded the rate of reaction. Activation parameters have been computed. Probable mechanism and the relevant rate law have been deliberated for the observed kinetic results.

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INTRODUCTION

Everyday a large amount of uncreated dyes and dye intermediates are discharged into the aquatic systems from various industries such as paper, textiles, inks, varnishes and paints without being processed. These contaminants result in high BOD, COD, toxicity, bad smell and coloration of water effluents [1]. The presence of color and its causative compounds are undesirable for domestic and industrial uses. Color is visible and can be an indication of pollution [2].

Acid yellow 36 is a mono azo dye and used as a coloring agent in many food industries. It is extensively used in the developing countries as a colorant in sweetmeat, ice-cream, soft drinks and beverages [3]. Due to its orange-yellow color, Acid yellow 36 is also widely used in the coating of turmeric. It is extensively used in paper, leather and many textile industries as a dye and also as colorant for the wool [3,4]. Moreover, it is widely used as a colorant for lacquers and cosmetic products. Furthermore, the dye is highly suitable for the preparation of colored water-fast inks [5] and can also be used analytically for the determination of trace amounts of Mo (VI) [6].

Dyes used in the textile industry may be toxic to aquatic organisms and can be resistant to natural biological degradation [7, 8, 9]. Hence, the decoloration of dyes has received increased attention. Several methods for treating effluents containing azo dyes have been developed which can be treated by some traditional methods such as biological, flocculation, and reverse osmosis, adsorption on activated carbon and ion exchange methods [10]. All these processes are expensive and complicated. Therefore, there is a need for inexpensive and simple methods to abolish harmful dyes in effluents. The oxidation of azo dyes has attracted much attention in recent years [11-13].

Aromatic N-halosulfonamides are mild oxidants containing a strongly polarized N- halogen bond where the halogen is in its +1 oxidation state. The prominent member of this group, chloramine-T (CAT) has been exploited as an oxidant for a variety of substrates [14, 15]. The species responsible for the oxidizing character may be different depending on the pH of the medium. The redox potential of the system is pH-dependent. CAT has been used as oxidant in neutral, acidic and alkaline media [16, 17]. It is also used as antiseptic and antipyretic drugs [18].

An extensive literature survey revealed that there are only a few reports on the kinetics of oxidation of organic dyes by CAT [19–21]. These facts were the reasons to undertake the study of kinetics of oxidation of Acid yellow by CAT in acidic medium with a view to elucidate the reaction mechanism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental:

The stock solution of chloramine-T (SDF CHEM LIMITED) was prepared in double distilled water and standardized iodometrically. Acid Yellow (AY36) dye (LOBA CHEMIE) was used without further purification. Aqueous solutions of desired strengths were freshly prepared prior to use. Other reagents were of analytical grade.

Kinetic measurement

The detailed kinetic measurement were performed under pseudo-first-order conditions with known excess of the $[CAT]_0$ over $[AY36]_0$ using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer single beam (Digital spectrophotometer 1200; LMSP, India). In the present study, the kinetic experiments were carried out between 293 and 309 K. A constant temperature was maintained with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ C$. Reactions were carried out in glass stopper Pyrex boiling tubes whose outer surfaces were coated black to eliminate any photochemical effects. For the standard run the oxidant as well as requisite amount of AY36, HCl and water were taken in separate tubes and thermostated for 30 min at 301K. The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of a measured amount of CAT to the stirred reaction mixture. Absorbance measurements were made at λ_{max} of 439 nm for AY36 dye for more than two half-lives. The absorbance readings at $t = 0$ and $t = t$ were taken as D_0 and D_t . Plots of $\log D_0/D_t$ versus time were made to evaluate the pseudo-first order rate constant k_{abs} which were found reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Effect of reactant concentration on the rate

The kinetics of oxidation of AY36 by CAT was investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants, under pseudo first-order conditions of $[oxidant]_0 \gg [substrate]_0$ with HCl medium at 301K. Under this condition for varying $[AY36]$ concentration, at constant $[CAT]_0$ and $[HCl]$, plot of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ versus time were linear ($r > 0.96$) indicating a first-order dependence of rate on $[AY36]_0$. The linearity of the plot with the constancy of the slope obtained at different $[AY36]_0$, confirmed the first-order dependence of rate on $[AY36]_0$. The pseudo first-order rate constants (k) obtained is recorded in Table 1. Under the same experimental conditions the rate of reaction increased with $[CAT]_0$ (Table 1) and plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [CAT]$ was linear ($r > 0.98$) with unit slope (Fig 1). This indicated that the order of the reaction was first-order with respect to $[CAT]_0$. Further, plot of $\log K$ versus $\log [CAT]_0$ was linear passing through the origin corroborating the first-order dependence on $[CAT]_0$. The rate of reaction reduced with increase in $[HCl]$ (Table 1) and plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [HCl]$ was linear ($r > 0.96$) with a slope of -0.25. (Fig 2) showing a fractional inverse-order dependence on $[HCl]$.

Table 1. The effect of varying [AY36], [CAT], [HCl] on rate of reaction.

$10^4 [\text{AY36}]_0$	$10^3 [\text{CAT}] \text{ moldm}^{-3}$	$10^3 [\text{HCL}] \text{ moldm}^{-3}$	$10^4 \text{ K}(\text{s}^{-1})$
1.2	2	3	4.030
1.4	2	3	4.244
1.6	2	3	4.000
1.8	2	3	4.054
2	2	3	4.172
1.6	1.6	3	2.053
1.6	2	3	3.970
1.6	2.4	3	4.189
1.6	3.2	3	5.222
1.6	4	3	6.387
1.6	2	1.5	5.119
1.6	2	2	4.504
1.6	2	3	4.000
1.6	2	4	2.198
1.6	2	5	2.006

Fig 1. Plot of log k vs log [CAT].

Fig 2. Plot of log k vs log $[\text{H}^+]$.

Effect of halide ion and p-toluene sulfonamide concentration on the rate

The addition of halide ions, Cl⁻ and Br⁻, in the form of their sodium salts (1.0×10^{-3} - 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) showed no pronounced effect on the rate. This indicated that the halide ions play no role in the reaction. The ionic strength of the reaction medium was varied from 0.1 to 0.4 mol dm⁻³ with NaClO₄ solution keeping other experimental conditions constant. It was found that addition of NaClO₄ showed a negligible effect on the reaction rate, representing the participation of nonionic species in the rate-determining step. Hence no attempt was made to maintain the ionic strength of the medium constant for kinetic runs. Addition of p-toluene sulfonamide (TSNH₂) to the reaction mixture (1.0×10^{-3} - 4.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) influenced the rate significantly by retarding the rate of reaction. The plot of log k vs [TSNH₂] (Fig4) gave a standard line with negative slope with fractional order indicating that TSNH₂ was not involved into the rate determining step of the proposed scheme.

Table 2. Effect of varying PTS reduction product on rate of reaction with [AY36]= 1.6×10^4 [CAT]= 2×10^3 moldm⁻³ [HCl]= 3×10^3 moldm⁻³.

10^3	10^4 K(s ⁻¹)	3+Log[PTS]	4+LogK
1.0	4.010	0	0.609
2.0	3.731	0.301	0.571
3.0	3.454	0.477	0.538
4.0	3.305	0.602	0.519

Fig 3. Plot of Log[PTS] vs Log k.

Effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the rate

The dielectric constant (D) of the medium was studied by adding MeOH (0-30 % v/v) to the reaction mixture with all other experimental conditions being held constant. The rate was not considerably altered. Values of dielectric constant of MeOH-H₂O mixture reported in the literature [22] were used (Table 3, Fig 4).

Table 3. Effect of varying dielectric constant on rate with [AY36]= 1.6×10^4 moldm⁻³ [CAT]= 2×10^3 moldm⁻³ [HCl]= 3×10^3 moldm⁻³.

ME OH(%V/V)	Dielectric Constant D	104 K(s ⁻¹)	1/D	4+LogK
0	76.73	4.000	0.0130	0.608
10	72.37	3.198	0.0138	0.504
20	67.48	2.3303	0.0148	0.362
30	62.71	1.919	0.0159	0.283

Fig 4. Plot of log k vs 1/D.

Solvent isotopic effects

Solvent isotope studies were performed in D₂O medium for reaction oxidation under standard conditions of [AY36] = 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Oxidant] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. The values of rate constant are found to be 1.011 × 10⁻⁴ the corresponding ratios in the rate k (H₂O) / k (D₂O) was 1.52. This indicates the fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer.

Effect of temperature on the rate

The reaction was studied at different temperatures (293-309k), keeping other experimental conditions constant. From the linear Arrhenius plot of log k vs 1/T (Fig 5) (r>0.99) composite activation parameters (E_a, ΔH[‡], ΔS[‡], ΔG[‡]) were computed for the oxidation of AY36 by CAT. These data are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of varying temperature dependence on the reaction rate and activation parameters for the oxidation of AY36 by CAT.

Temperature	10 ⁴ K(s ⁻¹)
293	1.909
297	2.952
301	4.007
305	5.997
309	6.525
E _a (KJmol ⁻¹)	31.675
ΔH [‡] (KJmol ⁻¹)	29.169
ΔG [‡] (KJmol ⁻¹)	93.783
ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-221.606

Fig5. Plot of effect of Temperature.

Test for free radicals

Alkenes monomers such as acrylonitrile and freshly prepared 10% acryl amide solution were added to the reaction mixture to initiate polymerization by free radicals formed in situ. The lack of polymerization indicated the absence of free radicals in the reaction mixture. This clearly ruled out the possibility of a free radical mechanism. The controlled experiments were also performed under similar reaction conditions without oxidant.

Stoichiometry

Stoichiometric experiments were conducted by mixing different ratios of AY36 dye and CAT in the presence of HCl at 301 K for 24 h. The results clearly demonstrated the consumption of 1 mol of AY36 per 3 moles of CAT. The observed reaction stoichiometry is represented as:

Characterization of products

The reaction mixture under standard concentration of CAT was kept in excess compared to that of AY36 dye and was allowed to progress for 24 h at 301 K. After the completion of the reaction, the mixture was neutralized with dilute NaOH and products were extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic products were identified by using the TLC technique and separated by column chromatography which revealed the formation of benzene and biphenyl amine as the oxidation products of AY36 and p-toluene sulfonamide (PTS) as the reduction product of the oxidant. These compounds were confirmed by mass spectral analysis (Fig 6).

Fig 6. Mass spectrum of *N,N*-biphenylamine at 170 and benzene at 79 amu.

The mass spectrum was obtained using electron impact ionization technique. The mass spectrum showed a molecular ion peak at 170 amu indicates the structure of bi-phenylamine and molecular ion peak of Benzene at 79 amu of the products of oxidation of AY36 (Fig 6). It was noticed that there was no reaction between the products and oxidant under the current set of experimental conditions.

REACTIVE SPECIES OF SODIUM N- HALO BENZENESULFOAMIDES.

Organic N-haloamines are sources of positive halogens and these reagents have been exploited as oxidant for a variety of substrates in both acidic and alkaline media [23]. Since organic N-haloamines have analogous chemical properties, it is predicted that identical equilibria exist in aqueous acidic and basic solutions of these compounds [24-27]. Chloramine-T acts as oxidizing agent in acidic and alkaline media [28] with a two electron change per mole giving p-toluene sulfonamide (PTS) and NaCl. The redox potential of CAT-PTS couple is pH dependent [23] and decreases with increase in pH of the medium (Energy of redox 1.138 V, 1.778 V, 0.614 V and 0.5 V at pH 0.65, 7.0, 9.7 and 12, respectively).

Reaction scheme

The suggested oxidizing species in acidified CAT solutions are TsNHCl, TsNCl₂, HOCl, and H₂OCl⁺

The reaction of protonation of TsNH₂Cl was reported by (S.S Narayana and V.R.S Rao. Radio Chem. Acta,(1983) 32, 1082 with protonation constant being 1.02 x10² at 25°C.If TsNCl₂ were to be the reactive species, then the rate lawwould predict a second order dependence of rate on[CAT]_o, which is incompatible with experimental observations. Since the rate of reaction is retarded by addition of TsNH₂, HOCl is the most probable oxidizing reactive species for the oxidation of Acid yellow 36(AY36) in the present study. From this discussion and experimental facts, scheme 1 is proposed to explain the reaction mechanism for the oxidation of Acid yellow36 by CAT in HCl medium.

Scheme 1.A general scheme for the oxidation of acid yellow 36 by CAT in HClmedium.

In the first step, TsNH₂Cl⁺ undergoes hydrolysis to give TsNH₂and HOCl. Here HOCl is the most probable oxidizing species for oxidation AY36. In the next step (rate determining step) the reactive species forms a complex (X) with AY36 (S) and finally complex formed undergoes a series of changes to give the oxidized products. If [CAT]_t is the total effective concentration of CAT, then

$$[\text{CAT}]_t = [\text{TsNH}_2\text{Cl}^+] + [\text{TsNHCl}] + [\text{HOCl}] \quad (12)$$

From equation of (8) and (9) of scheme 1,

$$[\text{Ts}^-\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+] = \frac{[\text{TsNHCl}] [\text{H}^+]}{k_1}$$

$$[\text{TsNHCl}] = \frac{[\text{TsNH}_2] [\text{HOCl}]}{K_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (14)$$

By substituting for $[\text{TsNHCl}]$ from equation (14) into equation (13),

$$[\text{TsNH}_2\text{Cl}^+] = \frac{[\text{H}^+] [\text{HOCl}] [\text{TsNH}_2]}{k_1 k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (15)$$

By substituting for $[\text{TsNH}_2\text{Cl}^+]$ and $[\text{TsNHCl}]$ from equation (13) and equation (14) into equation (15) and solving $[\text{HOCl}]$ will be

$$[\text{HOCl}] = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{CAT}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{H}^+] [\text{TsNH}_2] + k_1 [\text{TsNH}_2] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (16)$$

From equation (10)

$$\text{Rate} = k_3 [\text{HOCl}] [\text{S}]$$

By arrangement for $[\text{HOCl}]$ from equation (16), the following rate law is obtained.

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{CAT}] [\text{S}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{H}^+] [\text{TsNH}_2] + k_1 [\text{TsNH}_2] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (17)$$

Rate law equation (17) is agreement well to observed kinetic data which first order dependence of rate on $[\text{S}]$ and $[\text{CAT}]$ and inverse fractional order on each $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{TsNH}_2]$ on the rate of reaction .

CONCLUSION

Acid yellow 36 has been oxidized by chloramine-T in hydrochloric acid at 301 K. Stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 1:3. The oxidation product confirmed by MS analysis. Activation parameters are calculated. The scheme proposed and derived rate law has been correlated with the observed kinetic. The investigation was carried out spectrophotometrically and the oxidation of AY36 by CAT would be simple and inexpensive to remove the harmful dyes from effluents.

RECOMMENDED FUTURE RESEARCH

Kinetics of oxidation of a few azo dyes with CAT in presence of acidic medium carrying out. The oxidation of pure organic substrates (drugs) will be carrying out.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

AY36 Acid Yellow 36 dye
 CAT Chloramine- T
 PTS P.Toluene Sulfonamide

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